

3D printed cement-based repairs and strain sensors

Christos Vlachakis, Jack McAlorum, and Marcus Perry*

Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, United Kingdom

*Corresponding author. email address: m.perry@strath.ac.uk

Abstract

Concrete degradation is a significant challenge for asset managers, who are struggling to balance the need for monitoring and maintenance with the high costs and risks of manually deploying sensor and repair technologies. This paper presents 3D printed strain sensors based on alkali activated cement repairs, demonstrating a fixed-cost method for remotely deploying a combined monitoring and maintenance technology. Experimental protocols to quantitatively assess the compatibility of cements and printing processes are proposed. The strain sensing response of printed self-sensing cements is then investigated under compression and tension by monitoring changes in interrogated electrical impedance. Gauge factors for self-sensing repairs printed onto concrete substrates were 8.6 ± 1.6 under compression, with an average adhesion strength of 0.6 MPa between printed repair and concrete substrate. Gauge factors for repairs printed onto glass fibre reinforced polymers were 38.4 ± 21.6 under tension: these more variable than for concrete substrates due to incompatibilities between the cement repair and the polymer substrate. Hysteresis in the strain response was always observed, and strain sensing repeatability could be improved through cyclic loading. We also show that strain sensitivity can be adjusted after deployment by altering the configuration of interrogated electrodes. This proof-of-concept is a step towards monitoring and maintenance methods that are more compatible with the time and cost drivers of modern construction.

Keywords: printed sensors, cement printing, additive manufacturing, alkali activated materials, multifunctional materials, concrete repairs

1. Introduction

Civil asset managers have a clear need for tools that reduce the costs and risks of concrete monitoring and maintenance, so that they can ensure the continued resilience of ageing critical infrastructure. Self-sensing cements may provide one pathway to improving efficiency, as they act as traditional concrete binders and repairs [1,2] while also encoding local changes in strain [3], temperature [4] and moisture [5] as measurable shifts in their electrical impedance. Alkali activated materials (AAM) are a low-carbon alternative to ordinary Portland cements (OPC) that are particularly well-suited to self-sensing, as their inherently high electrical conductivity ($\sim 10^{-6}$ S/cm), negates the need to use electrically conductive additives [6–8].

Regardless of the material fabrication method, a self-sensing cementitious material needs to be deployed to produce one of the following:

- i) **Self-sensing structural element:** Here, the electrically conductive AAM/OPC matrix is mixed with aggregates to produce a self-sensing concrete cube or beam [11–13];
- ii) **Embedded cement-based sensor:** Pre-fabricated cement-based sensors (typically a small cube or beam) are embedded inside a larger cement-based element (such as a larger cube, beam or column) during casting [21] [19,22].

43 iii) **Retrofitted sensing coating:** Coatings are deployed, usually manually, onto existing concrete
44 substrates [3,4,9,10]. Measurands such as strain are transferred from the substrate to the
45 coating, with strain transfer efficiency mainly governed by the degree of adhesion between
46 the two materials [25], and coating thickness [9].

47 In high- and upper-middle- income countries, most concrete infrastructure has already been built. This
48 means that self-sensing coatings and repairs for existing concrete structures have larger potential
49 market than new self-sensing construction elements or semi-destructively embedded sensor
50 architectures. However, as with all sensors and novel materials, the retrofit of self-sensing AAM/OPC
51 repair poses practical challenges for industrialists. Manual deployment in a construction context is
52 expensive, places workers at risk, and leads to variable sensing performance due to human errors in
53 deployment. Additive manufacturing (more colloquially known as 3D printing) could provide the
54 answer to this deployment problem, as it allows for remote, automated and repeatable, deployment of
55 materials at fixed cost [14–17].

56 Despite this promise, there remain research questions in how 3D printing processes for cementitious
57 materials can be optimised for repair printing in a way that allows for optimisation and comparison
58 across independent studies. The first objective of this paper is therefore to outline and demonstrate a
59 new set of adaptable experimental protocols that allow the performance of printed cementitious
60 materials to be stated in more quantifiable terms. Following this, our second objective is to provide a
61 detailed characterisation of our printed repair’s strain-sensing performance, with a particular focus on
62 repeatability and hysteresis in the sensing response.

63 The work outlined here supports a technology which merges the benefits of self-sensing AAM repair
64 materials with additive manufacturing, In doing so, we demonstrate for the first time, 3D printed
65 patches that may in future support the de-risked, remote, and potentially autonomous deployment of
66 strains sensors and repairs in the construction sector.

67

68 **2. Background theory and methods**

69 **2.1 Alkali-activated materials**

70 Alkali-activated materials (AAM) are formulated by mixing aluminosilicate precursors (such as
71 metakaolin, fly ash or blast-furnace slag) with an alkaline activator solution comprised of a mix of
72 potassium (K^+) or sodium (Na^+) based silicates and hydroxides [32]. The alkali metal ions introduced
73 by the activator solution are the primary source of the self-sensing capabilities of AAM binders, as
74 they promote a high electrolytic conductivity that can be monitored via electrodes embedded in the
75 sample.

76 In this work, kaolin originating from Southwest England, UK, was calcined at 800 °C for 2 hours in
77 an electric furnace to produce metakaolin. This metakaolin was mixed at a 95:5 weight ratio with
78 90%-densified silica fume to produce a precursor. The chemical compositions of precursor materials,
79 measured via x-ray diffraction [3], are shown in Table 3. PVA fibres of 3 mm length were added to
80 the precursor (0.5 wt%) to reduce drying shrinkage [33] and to increase shape stability during printing
81 [34].

82 Sodium silicate (27.8% SiO_2 and 8.5% Na_2O) and sodium hydroxide (10M) were mixed at a mass
83 ratio of 2 to make the activator solution. The activator was poured into the dry components and mixed
84 for 5 minutes until a homogenous mix was achieved. The final precursor to solution ratio was 0.90,
85 and the density of the final uncured mix was 1.73 g/mL.

86 Table 3 – Chemical composition of precursor components.

Material	SiO ₂ (%)	Al ₂ O ₃ (%)
Kaolin	47	38
Metakaolin		87%
Silica fume	92.85	0.27

87 **2.2 3D printing of AAM**

88 The 3D printing set up is similar to that described in our previous work [cite old 3d printing
 89 temperature paper]. Briefly, a screw cavity extruder fitted with a nozzle of size 18G (0.84 mm) was
 90 mounted onto a commercial 3D printer with an x-y gantry axis (Figure 2). The uncured AAM was
 91 inserted into the syringe barrel and a pressure of 2 bar was applied to feed the material from the
 92 cartridge into the dispenser. The flowrate of extrusion was 2 mL/min, and the print speed was 30
 93 mm/s.

94
 95 Figure 2 - Cavity dispenser mounted onto x-y gantry axis.

96 A 3D CAD file of the intended objects was exported in stereolithography (STL) file format. Slicer
 97 software (Slic3r) was used to generate the required G-Code from the STL file, which defines the print
 98 paths and extrusion rates. Adjustments to the G-Code to include required time gaps were made by
 99 editing the code directly.

100 Two types of objects were printed for this investigation, buildability rings (see Section 3.3) and
 101 patches/overlays for adhesion and sensor testing (outlined in Sections 3.4 and 4.3 respectively).
 102 Figure 3 presents a typical data file for a buildability ring and the overlay. Buildability rings were
 103 comprised of up to 10 layers. Patches consisted of two layers, each of layer height 0.6 mm, deposited
 104 with a rectilinear infill density of 100 % and a 90° crosshatched infill pattern. A single perimeter was
 105 also added to close potential gaps at the patch's edges caused by the infill path to improve
 106 interlocking between the infill and the outer shell [35].

Figure 3 – G-Code representation of a) buildability ring and b) overlay for concrete substrate.

3. Parameters 3D printing cement overlays

The work in this paper originally had the single aim of demonstrating the printing of strain-sensing AAM repairs. Before we could achieve this, however, we discovered a need to assess and quantify the properties of our AAM mix so that we could optimise its mix design and printing parameters. To this end, we have modified a method originally put forward by Le et al. [31], to produce four essential parameters to assess the 3D printing of cement overlays:

- i. **Extrudability:** The ability of a mix to be continuously extruded as a continuous filament from a dispensing unit.
- ii. **Printability window:** Time limit in which the mix is printable and no blockage occurs.
- iii. **Buildability:** The ability of a material to maintain its self-weight and the weight of subsequent layers without noticeable deformation.
- iv. **Adhesion:** The bond strength achieved between the printed material and the substrate.

Furthermore, we have defined new experimental protocols to convert the originally qualitative descriptions of some of these parameters (in particular, extrudability and buildability) into experimentally measurable metrics that can be optimised.

Measurements of electrical impedance are also required in the present work to assess whether the printed specimen can be electrically interrogated, but this is discussed in more detail in Section 4.

3.1 Extrudability

Extrudability was broken down into two phases, both of which provide a true/false result. During phase 1, we test whether filament can be extruded for 10 seconds by the dispensing unit. The second phase involves printing three lines of filament with a length of 200 mm (each line separated by 4 mm). The 200 mm length was chosen to approximately match the intended lengths of features in our final application. If these longer printed lines were free from defects and had a consistent shape, then the mix was deemed extrudable.

The mix design described in Section 2.1 (with 0.5 wt% 3 mm PVA fibres) passed the phase 1 extrudability test. Other mixes which used higher quantities of PVA fibre (e.g. 1 wt%), longer PVA fibres (e.g. 6 mm), or stiffer fibres (e.g. carbon- or polypropylene fibres) did not pass the phase 1 test using our particular printing set up, so were discarded from further assessment.

Figure 11 depicts the outcome of the phase 2 test for the successful mix design candidate. As shown, the three lines maintained a fairly consistent shape and were free from major defects. Slight variations

139 in extruded thickness resulted from variations in levelling and entrapped air in the cement mix. This
140 extrudability test could be improved in future work by imaging these extruded lines or by measuring
141 their mass to better quantify variations in deposition rates and line thickness.

142
143 Figure 11 – Extrudability assessment of mix design by printing three 200 mm lines.
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145 3.2 Printability window

146 The printability window is a newly defined parameter that determines how long a mix can be
147 extruded without significant discontinuities. Our proposed test is essentially an extension of the
148 extrudability test: three lines with a length of 200 mm (4 mm spacing) were printed every 10 minutes
149 until major discontinuities were observed.

150 Figure 12 presents the results of the printability window test with the mix and printing parameters
151 described in Section 2. As shown, the printability window is 120 minutes, as the filament is
152 extrudable in a consistent manner for this duration. Small gaps that do appear are primarily due to
153 residual air bubbles in the filament. Beyond this 120 minute time frame, our mix suddenly became
154 difficult to extrude, as it hardened and clogged the dispenser.

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157 Figure 12 – Printability window test for 120 minutes at 10 minute intervals.
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159 For completeness, the open time of the AAM mix was measured using a Vicat needle as outlined
160 in BS EN 196-3:2016 [37]. The initial and final setting time of the mix were recorded as 16 hours and
161 20 hours respectively. This setting time is long compared to mixes used in most printing applications
162 in the literature, but mixes with prolonged setting times [34] are still usable. In general the setting
163 time of mixes is short (less than an hour) in mixes which have higher solid contents, fillers and
164 thickening agents [62,63].

165 The ongoing challenge in cementitious 3D printing is understanding how parameters like open time or
166 workability (measured using a standard slump test) can be used to optimise a 3D printing process in
167 which there are many coupled variables. These parameters are perhaps better suited to conventional
168 concrete mix design. Open time is, furthermore the only printing parameter directly referring to “time”
169 in Le et al.’s original set of printing parameters [31]. Diggs-McGee et al. [64] conducted an extensive
170 study to define the different categories of time in 3D printing. Time was classified as total construction
171 time, print time of layer, delay time and elapsed time of layer. Most studies primarily focus on the total
172 time to construct an object without considering potential faults and maintenance requirements in
173 printing. This is what we have attempted to address in the present work with our new protocols.

174 **3.3 Buildability**

175 Buildability in this work has been defined by extruding cylinders, or “buildability rings”, with a
176 diameter of 60 mm, as shown in Figure 3a and Figure 14. We can then define the buildability as:

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$$\text{Degree of buildability (\%)} = \frac{\text{Actual height of printed object}}{\text{Design height}} \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

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179 In this work, two sets of tests were conducted with time gaps of 1 minute and 3 minutes between
180 printed layers respectively. Ten rings were printed for each test and 10 height measurements were
181 made for each ring to assess the buildability as a function of the number of printed layers.

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Figure 14 – Ten-layer printed buildability ring.

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185 Figure 13 shows the degree of buildability for the mix printed with time gaps of 1 minute and 3 minutes
186 between layers. The degree of buildability starts at 98% but can drop as low 73% after 10 layers. This
187 signals that the previous layers are unable to fully support the weight of the newly deposited layers,
188 especially if they are not given much time to harden. This results in deformation and subsequently
189 incorrect filament deposition due to the increasing head distance. The maximum recommended
190 deformation allowed in buildability and shape retention tests ranges between 80-90% with structural
191 applications being at the higher end of this spectrum [57–59]. If we arbitrarily select a cut-off of 95%,
192 then Figure 13 suggests that we should not print any more than 2 layers.

Figure 13 – Degree of buildability for buildability rings between 2-10 layers with a time delay between layers 1 minute. Errors bars represent standard deviation of 10 measurements per sample for 10 samples.

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Note that when investigating the degree of buildability, it is important to keep a constant head distance between all objects. Different head distances can lead to different quality objects and ultimately different heights. Figure 5 presents four supposedly identical rings that have been printed with different head distances. As can be seen, as the nozzle’s distance from the bed increases, the quality of the printed object decreases. The head distance should be kept constant (equal to the layer height) during buildability tests to ensure consistency.

Figure 5 – Printed objects with different surface quality due head distance issues (head distance increases from left to right).

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As pointed out by Nerella et al. [60], when talking about buildability, the allowed deformations and tolerances should be based on the end application, to avoid the risk of overdesigning. In the current application, the intention is to produce self-sensing coatings on substrates. Deformation is allowable in this application as coatings are required to spread onto the concrete surface and anchor into the concrete capillaries to achieve a greater bond [61]. The mix and methods that we outline here will not be suitable for constructing structural elements. Indeed, the application discussed in the present work could be considered as 2.5D printing due to the relatively low thickness of the layers [56], although the terminology used does not affect our requirement to develop an quantifiable printing parameters.

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214 **3.4 Adhesion**

215 In the present work, adhesion refers to adhesion between the printed patch, and the concrete
216 substrate (rather than the inter-layer adhesion between printed layers [68]). Adhesion is required for a
217 self-sensing cementitious patch as it affects strain transfer from the substrate to the sensor, and because
218 the bond strength of the patches with the concrete is an indicator of their suitability for use as a repair
219 material.

220 Double-layered 90 mm × 90 mm patches were printed onto 100 mm concrete cubes (as shown Figure
221 8, concrete cube mix design given in Table 4). The top layer of the concrete cube surface was removed
222 with an electrical brush prior to printing to expose the aggregates to improve adhesion between the
223 patch and the substrate [38], and the concrete substrate was also pre-wetted [39] to avoid liquid
224 absorption from the concrete and thus excess liquid loss from the repair.

225 Table 4 – Concrete mix design for adhesion test.

Constituents	Weight
Cement	7.5 kg
Sand	10.5 kg
10 mm aggregate	13.35 kg
Water	3.375 l

226 The bond strength of the printed AAM patches onto concrete was evaluated using a pull-off adhesion
227 tester in accordance with BS EN 1542-1999 [40] at 6, 28 and 97 days after extrusion. The results,
228 presented in Figure 17 show no substantial change over the course of time. All coatings tested exhibited
229 adhesive failure at the interface between the patch and the substrate. Overall the average bond strength
230 of 0.6 MPa is low compared to manually deployed AAM repairs [33,53] but it is still within a
231 serviceable range for a non-structural repair material. While it could be inferred that the layer-by-layer
232 deposition may have affected the mechanical properties of the coatings [65], this could also be a result
233 of the surface preparation technique. The mean surface roughness of the concrete after wire brushing
234 (characterised using a Micro Epsilon Scan Control 2700-100) was 0.44-0.68 mm, which is relatively
235 low compared to that achieved in other studies that employ more aggressive techniques like
236 sandblasting [66].

Figure 17 – Adhesion strength of printed overlays at days 6, 28 & 97. Errors bars represent standard deviation of measurements for 3 samples.

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4. Strain sensing characterisation methods

4.1 Overview

With a printable cement patch in hand, we proceed to characterise strain sensing performance. The following AAM overlays were printed for strain sensor characterisation:

- Large square patches of footprint 90 mm × 90 mm printed onto 100 mm side concrete cubes (as shown in Figure 8).
- Small square patches of footprint 45 mm × 45 mm printed onto smaller 50 mm side concrete cubes.
- Rectangular patches of footprint 35 mm × 50 mm printed onto glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) test pieces. Figure 7 shows test piece dimensions and Figure 9 shows a printed patch on a GFRP test piece under tensile testing.

GFRP was chosen as an alternative substrate for strain characterisation it is an electrically insulating material that can be tested under tension, and it presents a linear stress-strain response in the loading range investigated in this paper. The material properties of the GFRP substrate are listed in Table 5. While steel substrates are more traditionally used in tensile testing, complete electrical insulation between a steel substrate and an AAM layer is difficult to achieve. Current flow in a steel test piece (and indeed the grips of the tensile tester) would make these components part of the sensing system. AAM and GFRP do, however, have poor adhesion compatibility, so sand was epoxied onto the ‘neck’ of the tester (area between $A \times W$ in Figure 7) prior to patches being printed in this region. This allowed the AAM patches to mechanically interlock with the sand.

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Figure 7 – GFRP test piece dimensions: A=60 mm, B=50 mm, C=50 mm, L=200 mm, T=8 mm and W=35 mm.

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Figure 8 – Large square patches printed onto concrete cubes. Images also show electrode orientation of patches: a) Layout 1 where measurement is parallel to applied load; b) Layout 2 where strain measurement is perpendicular to applied load

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Figure 9 – GFRP test piece hosting 3D printed rectangular AAM patch under tensile testing and interrogation.

Table 5 – Manufacturer’s values for properties of GFRP.

Tensile strength	Elongation	Density	Modulus of elasticity
160 MPa	3.5-5%	1.35 g/cm ³	5.5 GPa

Once patches were extruded onto substrates, stainless steel electrodes were inserted into the uncured AAM in the Van der Pauw (VDP) configuration [41], as shown in Figure 6. Once electrodes were inserted, samples were cured in containers at ambient temperature for 28 days.

4.2 Electrical impedance measurement

To prevent electrolysis at the electrodes, AAM samples are usually excited using an alternating voltage, $V(t)$. The resulting current response, $I(t)$, is measured and used to calculate the sample’s impedance:

$$\vec{Z} = \frac{V(t)}{I(t)} = Z [\cos(\varphi) + i\sin(\varphi)] = Ze^{i\varphi} \quad (Eq.3)$$

where $Z = |\vec{Z}|$ is the impedance modulus or magnitude, and φ is the phase difference between the current and voltage. There have historically been studies that use direct current to interrogate AAM sensors (i.e. they measure the sample’s electrical *resistance*, rather than its impedance). These studies risk inducing time-dependent changes in impedance due to interactions between alkali-metal ions and the electrodes.

While the VDP method provides an average measurement of patch impedance that is less sensitive to lead and contact resistances, the orientation of the electrical connections has important impacts for strain sensing [44]. To measure strain responses in the direction of the applied load, the voltage and

291 current should be applied and measured parallel to the applied load as shown in Figure 8a (i.e. voltage
292 is applied across electrodes 1 and 4 and current is measured across electrodes 2 and 3). This
293 configuration is denoted ‘Layout 1’. As part of a further investigation in this work, ‘Layout 2’ shown
294 in Figure 8b was also tested. In this configuration measurement is made perpendicular to the loading
295 direction, so we may expect to measure strains induced by the Poisson effect.

296 During mechanical testing, AAM patch electrical impedance was interrogated using an impedance
297 analyser in potentiostatic mode. Voltage excitations of amplitude 10 mV and frequency 5 kHz were
298 applied, and three measurements of the current response were obtained at each load state. The average
299 and standard deviation (error bar) value of the impedance modulus, Z , at each load state was then
300 calculated.

301 4.3 Mechanical testing for sensor characterisation

302 4.3.1 Factors affecting strain sensing

303 The strain sensing performance of self-sensing cementitious materials is affected loading rates
304 [18,45], temperatures during testing [22,46], moisture content of the sample [47–49] and filler
305 content (when present) [11,50,51]. Most of these factors have only been investigated in OPC binders
306 rather than in AAM. Nevertheless, previous studies on OPC were used to design the following
307 constraints for mechanical testing in this work:

- 308 ■ Samples were removed from containers and placed next to the testing apparatus for 15 hours
309 to allow them to equilibrate with the testing environment prior to testing.
- 310 ■ Experiments were conducted in a stable environment at constant temperature and humidity of
311 at 21.7 ± 0.2 °C and 33.9 ± 0.7 % respectively.
- 312 ■ Samples were not dried, and were wrapped in plastic film to avoid moisture evaporation from
313 AAM samples over the course of the test. Moisture facilitates ion migration (hence electrical
314 conductivity) within AAM sensors [7].
- 315 ■ Loading rates were kept constant.

316 4.3.2 Loading schemes

317 Figure 10 summarises the mechanical testing conducted in this work. Large scale concrete cubes
318 (sample set 2.2B in Figure 10) were tested using a 500 kN capacity load-controlled compressive tester
319 with 0.2 kN precision. The loading rate was 5 kN/s. All remaining sample sets (1.1, 1.2, 2.1A, and
320 2.2A) were tested using a displacement-controlled universal tester. The displacement rate applied was
321 fixed at 0.3 mm/min. A small preload was applied to all samples to eliminate any nonlinearity issues
322 that commonly occur at low loads [52].

323 For concrete compressive testing, electrically insulating GFRP sheets were placed between the
324 loading plates and the sample to avoid making the compressive tester part of the electrical circuit.

325 As shown in Figure 10, the strain sensing investigation was divided into an initial investigation (part
326 1) and the in-depth investigation (part 2). In part 1, the responses of printed AAM sensors were
327 investigated under compression and tension using GFRP test pieces. In part 2, compressive strain
328 responses were investigated using concrete cubes, and tensile strain responses were investigated in
329 more detail using GFRP test pieces.

330 The experiments summarised in Figure 10 made use of up to three time-dependent loading profiles,
331 described as follows:

- 332 ■ **Segment 1 (stepped).** Samples were loaded in 5-step increments and then unloaded in 5-step
333 increments. Each step was held for 1 minute to allow impedance measurements to be taken.
334 This loading cycle was repeated 6 times overall. For large concrete cubes under load-
335 controlled compressive testing (sample set 2.1A), the step size was 10 kN and the maximum
336 load was 50 kN. For displacement-controlled compressive tested samples, the step size was

337 0.02 mm and the maximum displacement was 0.1 mm. For tensile tested samples, the
 338 maximum displacement was 0.04 mm with a step size of 0.008 mm. All of the maximum
 339 values keep sample substrates within their linear-elastic regions.
 340 ■ **Segment 2 (cycling)**. Samples were cycled 40 times without steps between the minimum and
 341 maximum ranges of displacement described for Segment 1. Impedance measurements were
 342 not taken.
 343 ■ **Segment 3 (stepped)**. The Segment 1 loading pattern and measurement protocol were
 344 repeated after cycling.

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347 Figure 10 – Summary of the five mechanical tests conducted in this work, and the loading segments that were
 348 investigated during each test.

349 5. Strain sensing results and discussion

350 5.1 GFRP substrate strain sensing

351 Figure 18 shows time series of the fractional change in electrical impedance modulus, $\Delta Z/Z$, for
 352 AAM patches adhered to GFRP test pieces under tension and compression (sample sets 1.1 and 1.2 in
 353 Figure 10 respectively). The dynamic response of the impedance aligns with the expected behaviour
 354 of AAMs in both loading directions, but the repeatability and reversibility are clearly low, with the
 355 baseline impedance of samples at zero load increasing with each load cycle.

356 Reversible behaviour is difficult to achieve in cementitious sensors due to small changes in the
 357 microstructure of the matrix after a load is applied [47,69]. However, it has been found that
 358 reversibility and repeatability can be improved by imposing multiple load cycles on a sample prior
 359 strain characterisation [51]. Figure 19 presents the tensile strain sensing behaviour for an AAM patch
 360 adhered to GFRP under tension (sample set 2.2A). The responses during loading Segment 1 (prior to
 361 cyclic loading) and Segment 3 (post cyclic loading) are shown. Similar to Figure 18, these samples
 362 show repeatability issues during loading Segment 1, but repeatability improved after cycling loading.
 363 This suggests that there may need to be a period of “breaking in” or relaxation prior to using these
 364 sensors for structural health monitoring in the field.

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366 Figure 18 – Compressive and tensile strain sensing behavior of patches printed on GFRP during loading Segment 1.

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368 Figure 19 – Sensing response of patch printed on GFRP under tension for (top) loading Segment 1 (cycles 1-6) and
369 (bottom) loading Segment 3 (cycles 47-52).

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Figure 20 – Fractional change in impedance versus applied displacement for 3 load cycles under tension for GFRP.

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Figure 21 – Averaged (over 3 load cycles) fractional change in impedance versus tensile strain for patch printed on GFRP.

376 Figure 20 presents the impedance response for a GFRP sample post-cycling as a function of applied
377 displacement. The observed hysteresis phenomenon has been seen in cementitious strain sensors in
378 previous studies [11,22], but it is often underreported and its root causes are still not well understood.
379 Figure 21 presents the averaged impedance response of Figure 20 as a function of applied strain. As
380 shown, the gauge factor (GF) for this sample was 14.42.

381 While cyclic loading has made the repeatability acceptable within each sample, the repeatability
 382 *between* individual GFRP samples was low. Of the 5 samples tested, gauge factors ranged from 14 to
 383 65. This may be due to the inconsistent strain transfer imparted by the manually-deployed sand-epoxy
 384 layer. Overall, a high variation in GFs is common in filler-free AAM sensors, with reported gauge
 385 factors in other studies ranging from 20 to 2000 [11,50,70,71]. The fundamental reason could lie in
 386 strain's influence on ion exchange and conductivity in AAM, but while studies have been carried out
 387 [5,7,72], this concept is not understood to the extent where sensing performance of AAM binders can
 388 be reliably predicted. Further work in this field is required.

389 Finally, Figure 22 displays the sensing response for the instrumented GFRP under high levels of
 390 tensile strain. The behaviour is nonlinear as expected [73], as applying high loads compromises the
 391 structural integrity of the AAM patches, leading to cracking and debonding.

392 5.2 Concrete strain sensing: compression

393 5.2.1 50 mm cubes

394 Figure 23 presents the strain sensing response for 50 mm concrete cubes under compression (2.1A
 395 in Figure 10). Similar to GFRP test pieces, there are repeatability issues during Segment 1 that can be
 396 explained by minor damage in the patch, and the development (and gradual relaxation) of stresses at
 397 the interface between the substrate and the overlay upon each cycle [47]. After undergoing cyclic
 398 loading in Segment 2, sensing performance is more stable.

399 Figure 24 presents the fractional change in impedance as a function of applied displacement for all six
 400 load cycles in Segment 3. The 3D printed sensing patches again showcase hysteresis. GFs between
 401 samples were reasonably repeatable at 8.59 ± 1.55 . This is a better repeatability than that typical found
 402 for filler-free applications reported by other authors, where GFs range between 20-65 [11,70,74]. This
 403 may be because of the improved repeatability offered by the 3D printing process. The mean GF is
 404 lower than these previous studies, and this may also be a direct consequence of 3D printing, as we
 405 have found that it results in a lower adhesion strength between materials (see Section 5.2.3), and
 406 hence a lower strain transfer.

407 Figure 22 – Nonlinear sensing response of patch printed on GFRP under high tensile strain.
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Figure 23 – Sensing response of patch printed on 50 mm cube under compression for loading: (top) Segment 1 (cycles 1-6) and (bottom) loading Segment 3 (cycles 47-52).

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Figure 24 – Fractional change in impedance versus applied displacement for 6 load cycles under compression for 50 mm concrete cube.

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417 5.2.2 100 mm cubes

418 Changes in impedance were found to be consistent for patches printed onto 100 mm side concrete
419 cubes under loading. As displacement measurements were not acquired with this loading apparatus,
420 the stress sensitivity coefficient (SSC) was used to characterize the sensing performance of the
421 patches. Analogous to the gauge factor, this is defined as the fractional change in impedance per unit

422 applied stress. Figure 27 shows an average SSC for one sample of -0.046 MPa^{-1} . The average SSC
423 over all 3 samples tested was $-0.033 \pm 0.008 \text{ MPa}^{-1}$.

424
425 Figure 27 – Average fractional change in impedance versus applied stress for 100 mm concrete cubes for 6 load
426 cycles.

427 5.3 3D Printing: effect on strain sensing

428 To authors' knowledge, the effect of 3D printing on self-sensing cement strain sensing
429 performance has never been studied. However, we can draw analogues with mechanical performance:
430 for instance, it is known that printed cementitious materials present anisotropic mechanical behaviour
431 due to the weakened interface between layers and are thus affected by the direction of the applied load
432 in comparison to the direction of layers [65,75]. In the present work, AAM patches were printed
433 following a 90° crosshatched infill pattern (the first layer is deposited vertically, second layer
434 horizontally). This was done to create a more uniform patch that would be less sensitive to directional
435 effects.

436 The printed AAM was also highly workable to improve adhesion with the concrete substrate, and
437 interlayer adhesion between subsequently extruded material lines. Recent studies have also stated that
438 the rheological properties of a mix play a more important role on the mechanical performance of
439 printed binders rather the printing orientation compared to the applied load [76]. From this we can
440 tentatively suggest that strain transfer has been optimised to some extent given the current set up, but
441 more study of this area is required.

442 5.4 Sensitivity to electrode orientation

443 Finally, the strain sensing performance was investigated as a function of the electrode layout.
444 Referring to Figure 8b, electrodes were connected using Layout 2 and the 100 mm cube test
445 experiment (sample set 2.2B) was repeated. As shown in Figure 28, even though the sample is under
446 compression, the impedance increased (i.e. tensile strain was measured) with an SSC of 0.014 MPa^{-1} .
447 This value for the SSC is about 30% of the value noted for Layout 1 in Figure 27, suggesting that the
448 patch may now be measuring strains resulting from the Poisson effect. Further studies will be required
449 to investigate whether this is truly the case, but it is clear that the sensitivity to strain in one direction
450 can be reduced by swapping the electrode layout. This may be a useful technique for reference
451 sensing in future.

452

453 Figure 28 – Average fractional change in impedance versus applied compressive stress for 100 mm concrete cubes
 454 interrogated using electrode layout 2.

455

456 Conclusions

457 This paper presented new experimental protocols for comparing and optimising 3D printed
 458 cement repairs. The adhesion strength between the printed patches and concrete substrates was
 459 0.6 MPa, which is within the range required for a non-structural concrete repair. Alkali-activated
 460 material coatings were then printed onto concrete cubes and glass fibre reinforced polymer sheets, and
 461 their strain-sensing responses were investigated under compression and tension. These printed self-
 462 sensing cements exhibit a strain-dependent electrical impedance response without relying on the use
 463 of conductive fillers, and showcase a linear response at low loads. The sensors required multiple
 464 loading cycles before a repeatable strain response was achieved, and demonstrated hysteretic effects.
 465 Gauge factors for the sensors ranged from 8 to 60, with 3D printed patches on concrete substrates
 466 showing a high level of repeatability between samples. Future work will look to take this printing
 467 process out a gantry 3D printer so that strain sensing patches can be deployed more flexibly using
 468 extruders mounted to robotic arms.

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